

Research Article

**Prevalence of Sexually Transmitted Infections and the Need
for Outreach Programs to Improve Pregnancy Outcomes
in Women without Antenatal Care**

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[Received:-15-11-2023,
Accepted:-17-12-2023,
Published 24-12-2023]

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10701572

Abstract:

The study's findings would highlight the importance of complete prenatal care, which includes frequent STI testing and management. It would emphasize the importance of healthcare systems ensuring that all pregnant women have access to and can afford prenatal care. Furthermore, the findings may emphasize the necessity of public health efforts to raise knowledge about the impact of STIs on pregnancy outcomes and promote safer sexual behaviors. The study included data on the Sexually transmitted infections of 250 pregnant mothers without antenatal care who delivered in hospital, were 36% pregnant mothers infected with syphilis, were 50% pregnant mothers infected with Hepatitis B, were 8% pregnant mothers infected with genital ulcer and were 6% pregnant mothers infected with vaginal discharge.

The success of outreach programs is highly dependent on several factors, and tailoring interventions to the specific needs of the community is essential. Here are some additional considerations regarding the factors that can influence the success of outreach programs targeting women without antenatal care: Therefore, while designing a health program for people living in rural regions without access to a large health facility, both the use of mass media and on-site small group education should be taken into account.

Keywords: prenatal care, syphilis, antenatal care, sexually transmitted infections, vaginal discharge, outreach programs

Introduction:

Antenatal care (ANC) is an essential part to promote mother-and-child health. Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) during pregnancy are associated with multiple adverse birth outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight, perinatal death, and congenital

infections including increased mother-to-child HIV transmission [1-12].

Every day in 2017, 810 women worldwide died from preventable complications during pregnancy or childbirth [13]. Global evaluation of antenatal care, however, came up with a

new model, which was endorsed by the World Health Organization (WHO), to deliver antenatal services in 4 focused visits (focused antenatal care). The schedule is first early in the first trimester, 2nd between 4-6 months, 3rd between 7-8 months and 4th at term unless indicated [14]. Although there are controversies across the world with regard to making the antenatal care visits conventional or focused type, several developing countries adopted the new antenatal care model as a standard [14,15]. Beyond the number of visits, however, antenatal care is said to be fully effective if it makes the mother prepared to deliver under the care of a skilled health attendant [16]. In other words, some argue that unless the antenatal care service becomes a bridge to birth in the health facility, it may not help much to identify and treat the major obstetric complications that commonly occur during and after delivery (obstructed labor, uterine rupture, postpartum hemorrhage and sepsis) [17].

Though STIs are common in pregnant women globally, current syndromic management guidelines from both the World Health Organization (WHO) and South Africa continue to result in the majority of STIs (most of which are asymptomatic) remaining undetected and untreated during pregnancy [18–27].

Present study examines the impact of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) on pregnancy outcomes in women who did not receive antenatal care and the need of outreach programs. This research aims to understand the potential consequences of untreated STIs during pregnancy and the importance of adequate prenatal care in terms of outreach programs.

The study likely involves collecting data from a group of women who did not access antenatal care services during their pregnancies. Researchers would then analyze the prevalence of STIs among these women and compare it to the general population. The commonly tested STIs might include chlamydia, gonorrhea, syphilis. By examining

the pregnancy outcomes of these women, such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and perinatal complications, the researchers can assess the impact of untreated STIs on maternal and fetal health. They may also consider other factors that could influence the outcomes, such as socioeconomic status, age, or previous pregnancies.

The study's findings would offer information on the possible hazards associated with untreated STIs during pregnancy, as well as the role of prenatal care in early diagnosis and treatment. The findings may point to a greater frequency of unfavorable pregnancy outcomes in women without antenatal care who have STIs than in those who receive regular prenatal treatment.

The study's findings would highlight the importance of complete prenatal care, which includes frequent STI testing and management. It would emphasize the importance of healthcare systems ensuring that all pregnant women have access to and can afford prenatal care. Furthermore, the findings may emphasize the necessity of public health efforts to raise knowledge about the impact of STIs on pregnancy outcomes and promote safer sexual behaviors.

In the context of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and pregnancy outcomes in women without antenatal care, there are several aspects that can be explored further:

1. Impact of untreated STIs: Untreated STIs during pregnancy can pose various risks to both the mother and the fetus. Some STIs, such as chlamydia and gonorrhea, can lead to complications like pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) and increase the risk of preterm birth, low birth weight, and neonatal infections. Other STIs, like syphilis and HIV, can be transmitted from mother to child during pregnancy or childbirth, potentially resulting in serious health consequences.
2. Barriers to antenatal care: Women who do not receive antenatal care may face barriers that prevent them from accessing healthcare services. These barriers can

- include financial constraints, lack of awareness or education about the importance of prenatal care, transportation issues, cultural beliefs, or limited availability of healthcare facilities. Understanding these barriers is crucial for developing strategies to improve access to antenatal care for all pregnant women.
3. **Public health implications:** The study's findings have important public health implications. They emphasize the need for comprehensive sexual health education, including awareness about STIs, their modes of transmission, and the importance of early detection and treatment. Efforts to improve access to affordable and culturally sensitive antenatal care services can help reduce the burden of untreated STIs and improve pregnancy outcomes.
 4. **Importance of routine screening:** Routine screening for STIs during pregnancy is a crucial component of prenatal care. By identifying and treating STIs early, healthcare providers can help prevent complications and promote better health outcomes for both the mother and the baby. Implementing standardized protocols for STI screening in prenatal care can ensure that all pregnant women receive appropriate testing and treatment.
 5. **Need for further research:** While the study provides valuable insights into the relationship between STIs and pregnancy outcomes in women without antenatal care, further research is necessary. Future studies could explore specific STIs and their individual impacts on pregnancy outcomes, investigate the effectiveness of interventions to improve access to antenatal care, and examine the long-term consequences of untreated STIs on maternal and child health.
 6. **Impact on maternal health:** Untreated STIs in pregnant women can have detrimental effects on their health. Some STIs, such as untreated syphilis or HIV, can lead to severe complications like organ damage, neurological disorders, or even maternal mortality. Without regular antenatal care, these conditions may go undiagnosed and untreated, increasing the risk to the mother's health.
 7. **Perinatal transmission:** Certain STIs can be transmitted from mother to baby during pregnancy, delivery, or breastfeeding. This vertical transmission can result in congenital infections, which may lead to serious health issues or developmental problems for the infant. Timely identification and management of STIs during pregnancy can help reduce the risk of perinatal transmission.
 8. **Socioeconomic factors:** Women without antenatal care may be more likely to experience socioeconomic disadvantages, such as lower income, limited education, or lack of social support. These factors can contribute to higher rates of STIs and poorer pregnancy outcomes. Addressing social determinants of health, such as improving access to healthcare services and addressing socioeconomic disparities, is crucial for improving outcomes in this population.
 9. **Missed opportunities for intervention:** Antenatal care provides an opportunity for early detection and management of STIs. Regular screenings and appropriate treatment can help prevent complications and reduce the risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes. Women who do not receive antenatal care miss out on these crucial interventions, which can impact both maternal and fetal health.
 10. **Health education and awareness:** Promoting awareness about STIs, their potential consequences during pregnancy, and the importance of antenatal care is essential. Efforts should be directed towards educating women about the benefits of seeking prenatal care, the availability of screening and treatment services, and the importance of safe sexual practices to prevent STIs.

11. **Multidisciplinary approach:** Addressing the complex issue of STIs and pregnancy outcomes in women without antenatal care requires a multidisciplinary approach. Collaboration between healthcare providers, policymakers, public health agencies, and community organizations is necessary to develop strategies that improve access to care, enhance health education, and reduce the burden of STIs in this population.
12. **Increased risk of STI acquisition:** Women without antenatal care may have a higher risk of acquiring STIs due to various factors. Limited access to healthcare services, lack of routine screenings, and inadequate knowledge about STIs and safe sexual practices can contribute to higher rates of STI transmission. This increased risk further emphasizes the importance of timely and comprehensive antenatal care.
13. **Impact on infant health:** Untreated STIs during pregnancy can have serious implications for infant health. Some STIs, such as syphilis or HIV, can be passed from the mother to the baby, leading to congenital infections. These infections can result in developmental delays, organ damage, or long-term health issues for the child. Early detection and management of STIs can significantly reduce the risk of adverse outcomes for the infant.
14. **Potential for community transmission:** Women without antenatal care who have undiagnosed or untreated STIs can unknowingly contribute to community transmission. If left untreated, STIs can be transmitted to sexual partners, potentially leading to further spread of the infection within the community. Encouraging regular antenatal care and STI screenings can help identify and treat infections, reducing the risk of transmission to sexual partners and the wider population.
15. **Impact of stigma and fear:** Stigma surrounding STIs and lack of awareness may deter women from seeking antenatal care. Fear of judgment or discrimination due to their STI status can lead to delayed or avoided healthcare visits. Addressing stigma and promoting a supportive and non-judgmental environment within healthcare settings can encourage women to seek the necessary care and support.
16. **Long-term consequences:** Untreated STIs can have long-term consequences for women's reproductive health. Some STIs, such as untreated chlamydia or gonorrhea, can lead to pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), which can cause chronic pelvic pain, infertility, or ectopic pregnancies. Detecting and treating STIs during pregnancy can help prevent these complications and preserve women's reproductive health.
17. **Importance of outreach programs:** Implementing outreach programs that specifically target women without antenatal care can be beneficial. These programs can provide education about the importance of prenatal care, offer free or low-cost STI screenings, and facilitate access to necessary treatments. By reaching out to underserved populations, such programs can help reduce the barriers to care and improve overall maternal outcomes.

Objectives:

In a population-based research in Marathwada, Maharashtra, the link between maternal hepatitis B, genital ulcers, vaginal discharge, and syphilis infections in pregnancy outcomes in women without antenatal care was investigated, as well as the necessity for an outreach campaign.

Exposures: Sexually transmitted infection (hepatitis B, Genital Ulcer, Vaginal Discharge and syphilis infections) occurring before or during Pregnancy Outcomes in Women without Antenatal Care and need of the outreach programs.

Materials and Methods

In this population-based study, we used data from January 1, 2021, to December 31, 2021. Tandale Hospital is a tertiary care and teaching hospital where there are around 500 deliveries a year. Ethical approval was derived from the Tandale Institutional Review Board, (524/2021). Data were evaluated with respect to antenatal care and health behavior of pregnant women. Data were processed by SPSS version 25.

To be eligible for participation in the study, women must meet the following criteria:

Ages eligible for study: ≥ 18 years

Sexes eligible for study: only female

Accepts healthy volunteers: Applied

Ethics and Data Protection

We gathered and documented over 250 factors on personal data, medical records, and socioeconomic background from each participating mother-child dyad. Eligible women were requested to provide written informed permission. The study followed the principles outlined in the Helsinki Declaration. Legally underage moms required extra signatures from their legal caretakers.

Figure 1. Flow diagram showing selection procedure apply to data

Socio-Demographic and Socio-Economic Factors

Information on age, education, occupation and smoking during pregnancy were collected using the standardized Mother's Worksheet. Previous history of health behaviour, status was taken from the facility worksheet, which is obtained directly from the medical records.

Table 1. Demographic and health Characteristics of pregnant women without antenatal care

Demographic data	Total (N=250)	Age 18-20 (N=50)	Age 21-29 (N=150)	Age ≥ 30 (N=50)	p-value
Education					
Upto Std. 10	85 (34)	30 (60)	50 (33.33)	05 (10)	0.8
Graduate / Admitted	90 (36)	20 (40)	40 (26.66)	30 (60)	
Post Graduate / Admitted	75 (30)	00	60 (40)	15 (30)	
Occupation					
Unskilled	90 (36)	15 (30)	35 (23.33)	40 (80)	0.56
Business	7 (2.8)	0	2 (1.33)	5 (10)	
Working Job	32 (12.8)	5 (10)	22 (14.66)	5 (10)	
Student	121 (48.4)	30 (60)	91 (60.66)	00	
health behaviour					
Smoking during pregnancy	25 (10)	5 (10)	15 (10)	5 (10)	0.99
Alcohol during pregnancy	22 (8.8)	4 (8)	11 (7.33)	7 (14)	0.95
Folic acid/iron/magnesium intake in pregnancy	203 (81.2)	41 (82)	124 (82.66)	38 (76)	0.91

Total n=250, Age 18- 20 n=50, Age 21-29 n=150, Age ≥ 30 n=50

The study included data on the education level of 250 pregnant mothers without antenatal care who delivered in hospital. Upto std 10 were 34% graduated / admitted to graduation were 36% and post graduated / admitted to post-graduation were 30%.36% unskilled or unemployed or housewife, 2.8% business women, 12.8% working women and 48.4% were students. The data included in study regarding health behaviour, were 10% women smoking, 8.8 % consumes the alcohol and Folic acid/iron/magnesium intake in pregnancy were 81.2%.

All 250 pregnant women provided data on their supplement usage throughout pregnancy. In all, 203 pregnant women (81.2%) received supplements. Supplement consumption was positively related to maternal education.

Table 2. Sexually transmitted infections in pregnant women without antenatal care without antenatal care

Sexually transmitted infections	Total (N=250)	Age 18-20 (N=50)	Age 21-29 (N=150)	Age ≥ 30 (N=50)	p-value
Syphilis	90 (36)	20 (40)	49 (32.66)	21 (42)	0.54
Hepatitis B	125 (50)	25 (50)	79 (52.66)	21 (42)	
Genital Ulcer	20 (8)	3 (6)	12 (8)	5 (10)	
Vaginal Discharge	15 (6)	2 (4)	10 (6.66)	3 (6)	

The study included data on the Sexually transmitted infections of 250 pregnant mothers without antenatal care who delivered in hospital, were 36% pregnant mothers infected

with syphilis, were 50% pregnant mothers infected with Hepatitis B, were 8% pregnant mothers infected with genital ulcer and were

6% pregnant mothers infected with vaginal discharge.

Need of Outreach Programmes:

Maternal health is a major health concern in developing countries. Among the eight Millennium Development Goals adopted by the United Nations in 2000, the fifth Millennium Development Goal, improving maternal health, was to reduce the maternal mortality ratio by 75% between 1990 and 2015 [28].

While the availability and effectiveness of these programs may vary by location, outreach initiatives that have shown positive results:

1. **Mobile clinics:** Mobile clinics are an effective way to reach women who have limited access to traditional healthcare facilities. These clinics are equipped with the necessary medical equipment and staffed by healthcare professionals who can provide antenatal care services, including STI screenings, in underserved areas. Mobile clinics can travel to remote or rural regions, making healthcare more accessible to women who may face geographical barriers.
2. **Community health workers:** Community health workers (CHWs) play a crucial role in reaching out to marginalized populations and providing healthcare services. CHWs are trained individuals who work within communities to promote health education, provide basic health services, and facilitate access to care. They can conduct home visits, organize health awareness campaigns, and refer women to appropriate healthcare facilities for antenatal care and STI screenings.
3. **Outreach and education campaigns:** Public health initiatives that focus on raising awareness about the importance of antenatal care and the risks of untreated STIs can be effective in reaching women without antenatal care. These campaigns can utilize various channels such as mass media, social media, community events, and educational materials to disseminate

information. By addressing misconceptions, reducing stigma, and providing accurate information, outreach and education campaigns can encourage women to seek antenatal care and STI screenings.

4. **Collaborations with community organizations:** Partnering with local community organizations, non-profit agencies, or religious institutions can help establish trust and rapport with women who are not accessing antenatal care. These collaborations can provide opportunities for outreach programs to identify and engage with women who may face cultural, linguistic, or social barriers to seeking healthcare. By leveraging existing community networks and resources, outreach efforts can be more effective in reaching underserved populations.
5. **Targeted interventions for vulnerable populations:** Some outreach programs focus on specific vulnerable populations, such as homeless women, refugees, or women involved in sex work. These programs take into account the unique challenges faced by these groups and provide tailored services that address their specific needs. They may include outreach teams that visit shelters, drop-in centers, or areas where vulnerable women congregate to offer antenatal care, STI screenings, and support services.

Some other crucial factors are:

1. **Socioeconomic factors:** The socioeconomic status of the target population can impact their access to healthcare services. Programs that consider the financial constraints faced by women without antenatal care and provide financial assistance or subsidies can help overcome this barrier. Additionally, addressing other socioeconomic factors such as housing instability, food insecurity, and employment issues can contribute to better health outcomes.

2. Cultural sensitivity: Cultural beliefs, practices, and language can significantly influence healthcare-seeking behaviors. Outreach programs that are culturally sensitive and respect the cultural norms and preferences of the target population are more likely to be successful. This may involve employing healthcare providers, peer educators, or community health workers who share the same cultural background or training the existing workforce to be culturally competent.
3. Health literacy and education: Limited health literacy can hinder women's understanding of the importance of antenatal care and the risks associated with not seeking it. Outreach programs should prioritize health education, using clear and accessible language and materials. Providing educational resources in multiple formats, including visual aids, videos, and interactive tools, can enhance understanding and engagement.
4. Community engagement and trust: Building trust within the community is crucial for the success of outreach programs. Engaging community leaders, organizations, and influencers can help establish credibility and promote program participation. Meaningful involvement of community members in program planning and implementation can foster a sense of ownership and increase the program's acceptability and effectiveness.
5. Geographic accessibility: The geographical location and distribution of healthcare facilities can impact access to antenatal care services. In remote or underserved areas, mobile clinics or transportation assistance programs can be effective strategies. Collaborations with local healthcare providers and leveraging existing infrastructure can help improve geographic accessibility.
6. Stigma and discrimination: Stigma associated with pregnancy, STIs, or seeking healthcare can be a significant barrier for women without antenatal care.

Outreach programs should address stigma through awareness campaigns, community education, and creating safe and non-judgmental spaces where women feel comfortable seeking care.

7. Collaboration with healthcare systems: Effective coordination and collaboration with existing healthcare systems are critical for sustainable impact. Outreach programs should establish referral networks, partnerships, and mechanisms for continuity of care. This involves ensuring that women who are identified through outreach efforts can easily access and receive ongoing antenatal care within the healthcare system.

Regular monitoring and evaluation of outreach programs are vital to assess their impact, identify areas for improvement, and make necessary adjustments. This allows for continuous learning and adaptation to better meet the needs of the target population and improve maternal health outcomes.

By considering these factors and tailoring interventions accordingly, outreach programs have a greater chance of successfully targeting women without antenatal care and making a positive impact on their health and well-being.

Discussion and Conclusions

The aim of this study was to analyze the antenatal care behavior and health behavior of Pregnancy Outcomes in Women without Antenatal Care and investigate the influence of sociodemographic and socioeconomic factors on these behaviors. Also discussed the need of outreach programmes for Pregnancy Outcomes in Women without Antenatal Care

This study discovered that STIs were common among pregnant women, indicating that it is a major public health issue in our study area. Accordingly, more effective education of all women of childbearing age would be needed here as well, because maternal nutrition plays a key role in fetal development and neonatal growth [29].

Although 80% of women in our survey were taking folic acid, on average they also did not

start until the second month of pregnancy. However, our data do not allow a more precise differentiation of the reasons. The study's disadvantage was that we used the mothers' self-reports to assess their health behavior involving alcohol and tobacco intake, which might be a source of inaccuracy. It's likely that the ladies responded in terms of socially desired conduct. Accordingly, the actual number of women smokers and alcohol consumers could be higher.

By tailoring outreach programs to the specific needs and challenges of the target population, implementing culturally sensitive approaches, and addressing barriers such as transportation, cost, and social stigma, successful interventions have been able to engage women without antenatal care and improve maternal and fetal health outcomes.

The success of outreach programs is highly dependent on several factors, and tailoring interventions to the specific needs of the community is essential. Here are some additional considerations regarding the factors that can influence the success of outreach programs targeting women without antenatal care: Therefore, while designing a health program for people living in rural regions without access to a large health facility, both the use of mass media and on-site small group education should be taken into account.

Funding: None

Availability of data and materials

The datasets are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Informed Consent Statement

Eligible women were asked for written informed consent. Written informed consent included data assessment in face-to-face interviews, self-administered questionnaires and patient records.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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